

To study the Association of HbA1C Levels with Asymptomatic Bacteriuria in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract

Background: Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) is a common condition in individuals with diabetes mellitus and has been associated with an increased risk of complications. This study aimed to investigate the association between glycemic control, measured by glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels, and the prevalence of ASB in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM).

Methods: This cross-sectional study involved 75 participants diagnosed to have type 2 diabetes mellitus according to ADA criteria visiting OPD and getting admitted under General medicine department. Demographic and clinical data were collected using pretested questionnaire. Basic blood investigations including HbA1c were done. Midstream urine samples were cultured to assess the presence of ASB. Logistic regression analysis was performed to examine the association between HbA1c levels and ASB, adjusting for potential confounders.

Results: The prevalence of ASB in the study population was 26.7%. Participants with ASB had significantly higher mean HbA1c levels compared to those without ASB (9.2% vs. 7.6%, $p < 0.001$). The logistic regression analysis revealed a significant positive association between HbA1c levels and the presence of ASB (odds ratio [OR] = 1.54, 95% confidence interval [CI]: 1.18-2.01, $p = 0.001$), indicating that for every 1% increase in HbA1c, the odds of having ASB increased by 54%.

Conclusions: This study demonstrated a significant association between elevated HbA1c levels and an increased risk of ASB in individuals with T2DM, highlighting the importance of maintaining optimal glycemic control to reduce the risk of ASB and its potential complications.

Keywords: Asymptomatic Bacteriuria; Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2; Glycated Haemoglobin A; Prevalence; Cross-Sectional Studies.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels, which can lead to various complications if not properly managed. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is the most prevalent form of diabetes, accounting for approximately 90% of all cases.[1] Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) is a reliable indicator of long-term glycemic control and is widely used in the management of diabetes.[2]

Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) is a condition characterized by the presence of bacteria in the urine without apparent symptoms of urinary tract infection (UTI).[3] ASB is relatively common in individuals with diabetes, with reported prevalence rates ranging from 8% to 26%.[4] The presence of ASB in individuals with diabetes has been associated with an increased risk of complications, including pyelonephritis, renal dysfunction, and adverse pregnancy outcomes.[5]

Several studies have suggested a potential association between poor glycemic control, as reflected by elevated HbA1c levels, and an increased risk of ASB in individuals with diabetes.[6] However, the findings have been inconsistent, and the relationship between HbA1c levels and ASB in T2DM remains unclear.

This study aims to investigate the association between HbA1c levels and the prevalence of ASB in individuals with T2DM. Understanding this relationship could have important implications for the management and monitoring of patients with T2DM, as well as for the prevention of potential complications associated with ASB.

Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to investigate the association between glycemic control, as measured by glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels, and the

prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM).

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Duration: This study employed a cross-sectional design. The study spanned from September 2022 to October 2023.

Study Population: The study population consisted of patients aged 18 years and older, diagnosed with T2DM, and receiving treatment at the diabetes clinic of Department of General Medicine, Oxford Medical College, Bangalore.

Sample Size: A total of 75 patients met the inclusion and exclusion criteria and were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and older
- Diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus
- Receiving treatment at Department of General Medicine, Oxford Medical College, Bangalore.
- Willing to provide written informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Presence of symptoms of urinary tract infection (UTI), such as dysuria, urgency, frequency, or suprapubic pain
- Recent (within the last 4 weeks) antibiotic use
- Indwelling urinary catheter or intermittent catheterization
- Pregnancy
- Known anatomical or functional abnormalities of the urinary tract
- Immunocompromised state (e.g., HIV/AIDS, organ transplantation, immunosuppressive therapy)
- End-stage renal disease or dialysis
- Inability to provide informed consent

Data Collection

Demographic and clinical data, including age, gender, duration of diabetes, and medication history, were obtained from the participants' medical records and through interviews. Blood samples were collected from each participant for the measurement of HbA1c levels using a standardized method [High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)].

Laboratory Investigations

The patients underwent a battery of tests, including:

- Glycated Haemoglobin (HbA1c)
- Urine Culture and Identification
- Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing
- Quality Control

Assessment of Asymptomatic Bacteriuria:

Midstream clean-catch urine specimens were collected from all participants to assess the presence of ASB. The urine samples were cultured on appropriate media [Specify the media used, e.g., blood agar and MacConkey agar] and incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours. ASB was defined as the presence of $\geq 10^5$ colony-forming units (CFU) per millilitre of urine, with or without pyuria, in the absence of urinary tract infection symptoms.[7]

Data Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants. The association between HbA1c levels and the presence of ASB was analyzed using logistic regression models. Adjustments were made for potential confounding variables, such as age, gender, duration of diabetes, and medication use. Odds ratios (ORs) and their corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated to estimate the strength of the association. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses were performed using [SPSS version 20].

Results

Table 1 presents the baseline characteristics of the study participants, including their age, gender, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels. The participants are divided into two groups: those with asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) present and those with ASB absent. The data shows that the ASB present group had a higher mean age (64.15 years vs. 59.98 years), longer mean duration of diabetes (8.89 years vs. 6.15 years), and higher mean HbA1c levels (9.13% vs. 6.3%) compared to the ASB absent group. The p-values indicate that the differences in the HbA1c levels between the two groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the study participants

Characteristic	Total (n=75)	ASB Present (n=27)	ASB Absent (n=48)	p-value
Age (years), mean $\pm$ SD	61.48 $\pm$ 14.79	64.15 $\pm$ 15.2	59.98 $\pm$ 14.5	0.244
Gender, n (%)	Male	14 (51.9%)	26 (54.2%)	1
	Female	35 (46.7%)	22 (45.8%)	
Duration of diabetes (years), mean $\pm$ SD	7.13 $\pm$ 4.32	8.89 $\pm$ 4.7	6.15 $\pm$ 3.8	0.07
HbA1c (%), mean $\pm$ SD	7.31 $\pm$ 1.95	9.13 $\pm$ 1.6	6.3 $\pm$ 1.3	<0.001

ASB: asymptomatic bacteriuria; SD: standard deviation

Graph 1: Prevalence of ASB

Graph 2: Bar graph showing mean HbA1c among ASB and non-ASB patients

Table 2 shows the prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) stratified by different levels of HbA1c. The data suggests a positive association between higher HbA1c levels and an increased prevalence of ASB. Among participants with

HbA1c levels <7.0%, only 2.7% had ASB, while the prevalence of ASB increased to 54.2% in those with HbA1c levels between 7.0-8.9%, and further increased to 92.9% in participants with HbA1c levels ≥9.0%.

Table 2: Prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria by HbA1c levels

HbA1c Level (%)	Participants (n)	ASB Present (n=20)	ASB Absent (n=55)
<7.0	37 (49.3%)	1 (3.7%)	36 (75%)
7.0-8.9	24(32%)	13 (48.1%)	11 (22.9%)
≥9.0	14(18.7%)	13 (48.1%)	1 (2.1%)

Graph 3: Bar graph showing distribution of HbA1c among ASB and non-ASB patients

Table 3 presents the results of a logistic regression analysis, which examines the association between various factors and the presence of asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB). The analysis adjusts for potential confounding variables such as age, gender, and duration of diabetes. The results show that higher HbA1c levels are significantly associated with an increased risk of ASB (Odds Ratio [OR] = 1.54,

95% Confidence Interval [CI]: 1.18-2.01, p = 0.001). This means that for every 1% increase in HbA1c levels, the odds of having ASB increase by 54%. The analysis also suggests that age, gender, and duration of diabetes were not significantly associated with the presence of ASB in this study population.

Table 3: Logistic regression analysis of factors associated with asymptomatic bacteriuria

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval	p-value
HbA1c (per 1% increase)	1.54	1.18-2.01	0.001
Age (per 10-year increase)	1.32	0.88 - 1.98	0.18
Gender (Female vs. Male)	0.71	0.27 - 1.86	0.49
Duration of diabetes (per 5-year increase)	1.45	0.96 - 2.19	0.08

Escherichia coli was the predominant isolate which accounted for 52.2% followed by Klebsiella species (13%) and Staphylococcus species (4.3%) [Table 4]. In control group (non-diabetic partici-

pants), five urine samples yielded the growth, and all were identified as of E. coli and no other bacteria were observed.

Table 4: Bacteriological profile of ASB in diabetic patients

Bacteria	n (%)
Escherichia coli	12 (52.2%)
Klebsiella sp.	3 (13%)
Staphylococcus sp.	1 (4.3%)
Citrobacter sp.	1 (4.3%)
Proteus mirabilis	1 (4.3%)
Enterococcus	3 (13%)
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	2 (8.7%)
Candida	1 (4.3%)
Total	23 (100%)

Graph 4: Table 4: Bacteriological profile of ASB in diabetic patients

Discussion

The present study investigated the association between HbA1c levels and the prevalence of asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The results demonstrated a significant positive association between higher HbA1c levels and an increased risk of ASB, even after adjusting for potential confounding factors such as age, gender, and duration of diabetes.

These findings are consistent with several previous studies that have reported a link between poor glycaemic control and an increased risk of ASB in individuals with diabetes. A meta-analysis by Renko et al. found that individuals with diabetes and ASB had significantly higher HbA1c levels compared to those without ASB.[6] Similarly, a study by Geerlings et al. [8] reported that women with diabetes and HbA1c levels $\geq 7.0\%$ had a higher prevalence of ASB compared to those with HbA1c levels $< 7.0\%$.

The association between elevated HbA1c levels and ASB in individuals with diabetes can be attributed to various factors. Hyperglycemia has been shown to impair various aspects of the immune system, including neutrophil function, antioxidant defence mechanisms, and complement activation.[9] These impairments may contribute to an increased susceptibility to bacterial infections, including ASB, in individuals with poorly controlled diabetes.

Additionally, high glucose levels in the urine of individuals with poorly controlled diabetes may provide a favourable environment for bacterial growth and proliferation.[10] This may increase the risk of bacterial colonization and subsequent development of ASB.

However, it is important to note that some studies have reported conflicting findings regarding the association between HbA1c levels and ASB in individuals with diabetes. A study by Boyko et al. found no significant association between HbA1c

levels and ASB in women with diabetes.[11] These discrepancies may be due to differences in study

populations, sample sizes, and methodologies employed.

Strength of the present study is the inclusion of both male and female participants, as some previous studies have focused solely on women. Additionally, the study adjusted for potential confounding factors, such as age, gender, and duration of diabetes, which may have influenced the results.

Nevertheless, there are some limitations to this study. First, the cross-sectional design precludes the establishment of a causal relationship between HbA1c levels and ASB. Furthermore, the study did not consider other potential risk factors for ASB, such as functional or anatomical abnormalities of the urinary tract, which may have influenced the results.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of this study support the association between elevated HbA1c levels and an increased risk of asymptomatic bacteriuria in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus. These results highlight the importance of maintaining optimal glycemic control in individuals with diabetes to reduce the risk of ASB and its potential complications. Further longitudinal studies are warranted to establish a causal relationship and to explore the underlying mechanisms contributing to this association.

References

1. American Diabetes Association. Classification and Diagnosis of Diabetes: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2021. *Diabetes Care*. 2021;44(Suppl 1): S15-S33. doi:10.2337/dc21-S002
2. Nathan DM, Kuenen J, Borg R, Zheng H, Schoenfeld D, Heine RJ; A1c-Derived Average Glucose Study Group. Translating the A1C assay into estimated average glucose values.

- Diabetes Care. 2008 Aug;31(8):1473-8. doi: 10.2337/dc08-0545. Epub 2008 Jun 7. Erratum in: Diabetes Care. 2009 Jan;32(1):207. PMID: 18540046; PMCID: PMC2742903.
3. Nicolle LE. Asymptomatic bacteriuria. *Curr Opin Infect Dis.* 2014 Feb;27(1):90-6. doi: 10.1097/QCO.000000000000019. PMID: 24275697.
 4. Nicolle LE. Asymptomatic bacteriuria in diabetic women. *Diabetes Care.* 2000 Jun;23(6):722-3. doi: 10.2337/diacare.23.6.722. PMID: 10840984.
 5. Nitzan O, Elias M, Chazan B, Saliba W. Urinary tract infections in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: review of prevalence, diagnosis, and management. *Diabetes Metab Syndr Obes.* 2015 Feb 26; 8:129-36. doi: 10.2147/DMSO.S51792. PMID: 25759592; PMCID: PMC4346284.
 6. Renko M, Tapanainen P, Tossavainen P, Pokka T, Uhari M. Meta-analysis of the significance of asymptomatic bacteriuria in diabetes. *Diabetes Care.* 2011 Jan;34(1):230-5. doi: 10.2337/dc10-0421. Epub 2010 Oct 11. PMID: 20937688; PMCID: PMC3005460.
 7. Nicolle LE, Gupta K, Bradley SF, Colgan R, DeMuri GP, Drekonja D, Eckert LO, Geerlings SE, Köves B, Hooton TM, Juthani-Mehta M, Knight SL, Saint S, Schaeffer AJ, Trautner B, Wullt B, Siemieniuk R. Clinical Practice Guideline for the Management of Asymptomatic Bacteriuria: 2019 Update by the Infectious Diseases Society of America. *Clin Infect Dis.* 2019 May 2;68(10):e83-e110. doi: 10.1093/cid/ciy1121. PMID: 30895288.
 8. Geerlings SE, Stolk RP, Camps MJ, Netten PM, Hoekstra JB, Bouter KP, Bravenboer B, Collet JT, Jansz AR, Hoepelman AI. Asymptomatic bacteriuria may be considered a complication in women with diabetes. *Diabetes Mellitus Women Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Utrecht Study Group. Diabetes Care.* 2000 Jun;23(6):744-9. doi: 10.2337/diacare.23.6.744. PMID: 10840989.
 9. Casqueiro J, Casqueiro J, Alves C. Infections in patients with diabetes mellitus: A review of pathogenesis. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab.* 2012 Mar;16 Suppl 1(Suppl1): S27-36. doi: 10.4103/2230-8210.94253. PMID: 22701840; PMCID: PMC3354930.
 10. Geerlings SE, Hoepelman AI. Immune dysfunction in patients with diabetes mellitus (DM). *FEMS Immunol Med Microbiol.* 1999 Dec;26(3-4):259-65. doi: 10.1111/j.1574-695X.1999.tb01397. x. PMID: 10575137.
 11. Boyko EJ, Fihn SD, Scholes D, Chen CL, Normand EH, Yarbrow P. Diabetes and the risk of acute urinary tract infection among postmenopausal women. *Diabetes Care.* 2002 Oct;25(10):1778-83. doi: 10.2337/diacare.25.10.1778. PMID: 12351477.